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Research Article

**AWARENESS ABOUT TYPE 2 DIABETES AND
ASSESSMENT OF DIETARY COMPLIANCE**¹Amna Arshad, ¹Nimra Shams, ²Dr Ata Ullah¹Allied Hospital Faisalabad²DHQ Hospital Layyah**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

Disease named Type 2 diabetes is most spread disease nowadays in whole world including Pakistan. So as we know that best treatment of diabetes is to control our diet, and to control diet we have to show complete knowledge about disease, its harmful effects and how can we stable and manage increasing ratio of disease. If we will do all these precautions, we can control our diabetes. Type 2 diabetes effects patient's health a lot so we have to cheer up those patients who are suffering from this disease. There was an experiment held between diabetic patients, there was a question answer segment between people who was infected with type two diabetes there was a approximately 460 people who fill up about 300 answers of the questions. With this experiment we see positive results, we find different ratios in result like 0.140 was those patients who know about diet we have to take in diabetes. People who was aware with type 2 diabetes was 0.445 .0.300 was those who contain diet complaisance. So we concluded that patients who are suffering from type 2 diabetes and got admission in hospital of Lahore is just because of irregular and there unbalanced diet. Doctors help them to know about their disease and a proper guideline to treat their disease by themselves.

Key Words: Type 2 diabetes, treatment, awareness, diet complaisance, drawbacks.

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INTRODUCTION:

As we all know that diabetes is a disease which effect whole world either they are developing countries or developed [1]. All of the countries affected with this disease, are trying to treat type 2 diabetes. Countries affected with disease like Canada, USA, India and Pakistan also try to treat this disease [2]. There are different diseases which are harmful for human being as heart attacks, caners, and diabetes is also one of them [3]. Pakistan is not well-developed country, so people do not have much more knowledge about their disease, due to this unawareness about disease, their health and mind started declining. So now our main aim is to aware people about type 2 diabetes and its side effects, and its safety precautions too, to avoid this disease and prevent people from more damage [4]. When people will start taking care by themselves or the people living around these patients will have full knowledge about disease, they will help them to get cure with this disease and we can smoothly cure and make end of this disease [5]. When we feel any type of even fever, we need our loved ones with us for our support so same for this type 2 diabetes, people who are facing this long-lasting disease need support of their family members, people living around them, when they will feel that people love them and they will automatically start motivating their selves and will move towards life more efficiently and more heartily[6]. In type 2 diabetes, which type of food people are taking is most important point because diet effects the level of sugar to increase or decrease. In a hospital located in Lahore studied that for sugar patients or those who are suffering with type 2 diabetes must have to take care of their diet, because when their diet will not be balanced, they cannot get rid of this deadly disease [7]. This research is taken from a hospital of Lahore where diabetic patients go for daily check up and tell about their daily activities like which type of diet they take, their routine activities, behavior of people living around them etc.

(Table: 1)

Variables		N	%
Gender	Male(M)	164	54.7
	Female(F)	136	45.3
	Total	300	100
Age	15-24 years	9	3
	25-34 years	60	20
	35-44 years	113	37.7
	45-55 years	54	18
	55 or above	64	21.3
	Total	300	100
Hospital name	Mayo hospital	103	34.3
	Lahore care hospital	94	31.3

METHODS:

Methodology which we used to get feedback about type 2 diabetes and its treatment was Question answers session and this whole experiment done in 3 months in a hospital of Lahore where patients come their regular treatment. Patients was in big amount and most of them was not having any type of knowledge about their disease, so by filling up these Performa, researchers was able to know about the main problems of diabetic patient. Researches collect data in 2 different form in the shape of primary and secondary data, in primary form of data, questions asked to the patients about their disease and its treatment like which type food they have to take or avoid, they activities either physical or mental. On the other hand they also review them about essays and articles which were about type 2 diabetes. Both of this experiment was about to aware people about their disease. After the experiment, they send it to SPSS and after further process of these sampling which given from the patients who was treating with diabetes and was able to cure their disease. With the help of these articles and research of these three months people was able to know about their disease, and what they have to take in their diet, what is good and what is bad, they able to know but we have to spread awareness about this disease because as we all know that Pakistan is a developing country and most of people are un educated, so by spreading awareness about type 2 diabetes we will save a lot of lives.

RESULTS:

There were total 300 people who were diabetic patients where 155 were males and 145 were females. In Mayo hospital Lahore 103 respondents was found. 94 was from Lahore care hospital and 103 were from Jinnah hospital. In these 300 patients only 34 was those who was suffering with type 2 diabetes, other was suffering from other harmful diseases. Ratio and detail of whole experiment shown in the table give below.

	Jinnah hospital	103	34.3
	Total	300	100

Table 2 is showing the correlation between dependent and independent variables.

(Table: 2) Correlation among studied variables.

		Knowledge on Diabetic diet	Health/education awareness	Dietary compliance	Diabetic patient
Knowledge on Diabetic diet	Pearson correlation	1	.250**	.036	.150**
	N	300	300	300	300
Health/education awareness	Pearson correlation	.250**	1	.414**	.446**
	N	300	300	300	300
Dietary compliance	Pearson correlation	.036	.414**	1	.305**
	N	300	300	300	300
Diabetic patient	Pearson correlation	.150**	.446**	.305**	1
	N	300	300	300	300

(Table:3)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.468 ^a	.219	.211	1.47728

a. Predictor: (Constant) ,Dietary compliance, Knowledge on Diabetic Diet , Health education/awareness.

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	180.867	3	60.289	27.626	.0000 ^a
	Residual	645.976	296	2.182		
	Total	826.843	299			

a. Predictors: (Constant) ,Dietary compliance, Knowledge on Diabetic Diet, Health education/awareness.

b. Dependent Variable: Diabetic Patient

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Beta	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.582	.520	1.56	3.044	.003
	Knowledge on Diabetic Diet	.082	.083	.052	.985	.325
	Health Education/awareness	.447	.071	.370	6.339	.000
	Dietary compliance	.199	.075	.150	2.655	.008

DISCUSSION:

To cure type 2 diabetes, first step is to spread awareness about this disease [8]. By spreading awareness among the people in Mayo hospital, Lahore, their health will be improve, they will show more enthusiasm toward fight with this disease [9]. With patients we also have to aware other people ,in this way they will take care of their own diets as well as with diabetic patients. Diabetes is one of those diseases which show its side effects after collapsing body, care before disease will be more helpful to reduce the graph of type 2 diabetes in Pakistan [10]. To have proper

and complete knowledge about the disease by reading articles or by educational activities help people a lot to maintain their diet and start self-assessment in which they think which type of physical activities they are doing and which type of diet they are taking, their mental situation and their stage of disease [11]. People who got effected with diabetes is mostly age between 45-60,so most of them are uneducated, they do not have any how know about their disease so this type of awareness and guidelines help those type of people and ensure them that they can treat and control their diabetes by themselves by doing some important activities

and proper diet[12]. Due to diabetes and changing start to happen in their lives make them depressed, usually patients after diabetes, due to over thinking and over stress many other type of disease born in them. Like high cholesterol level, mental stress, psychological disorders or heart attacks so this awareness is must to save lives from many other diseases [13]. By applying all these rules as by spreading awareness, complete knowledge about disease, diet plan, what they have to eat and what they don't have to eat, people living around them should do care of them, people will get rid of this disease by following all these rules[14]. But our main problem is that mostly people who have diabetes are uneducated so it's very difficult to spread this awareness, still there is a large number of patients present in Mayo hospital, Lahore were patients come for their daily checkup and due to not taking proper diet, their level of diabetes is increasing.

CONCLUSION:

Most of patients who is suffering with type 2 diabetes, do not go to hospital, so it is concluded that the patients who is going to hospitals for their regular checkup, they have some awareness about disease so Mayo hospital should take care of them and give them proper awareness about their disease which will be helpful for them to control their diet and treat their disease.

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